

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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COMPARISON OF THE BRADLEY METHOD® AND HYPNOBIRTHING®
CHILDBIRTH EDUCATION CLASSES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this doctoral project was to develop a manuscript that compares and contrasts two forms of childbirth education, Hypnobirthing® (The Mongan Method) and the Bradley Method® (husband-coached natural childbirth).

Through the literature reviewed, it was found that the Bradley Method involves a longer set of classes intended to educate on multiple components. HypnoBirthing focuses mainly on relaxation for self-hypnosis, the natural birth process, and releasing fears related to pregnancy and childbirth. Pain management during childbirth is also controlled differently; with the Bradley Method using the support of a coach to cope and HypnoBirthing using self-hypnosis to control the degree and manner in which a woman feels the contractions of labor and the process of birth.

The manuscript is eight pages with three tables that cover the main points, class content, and evidence outcomes of both methods. The manuscript will be submitted to *the Journal of Perinatal Education (JPE)* for publication. *JPE* is a peer-reviewed journal that specifically focuses of ante, intra, and postpartum education to increase the knowledge of educators and other healthcare professionals. Readers of this journal include childbirth educators, nurses, midwives, and physicians. If published, the readers can use the tables in the article as patient teaching tools. This allows the content to be easily broken down so that each woman can understand the similarities and differences.

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BACKGROUND

Problem Statement

In the last century, birth in the United States has been taken from a natural process in most women's lives to a medicalized procedure similar to one of disease management with multiple "interventions" (Hinote & Wasserman, 2012; Romano & Lothian, 2008). Since the 1960s, a small group of women and providers have tried to bring the ownership of birth back to women by supporting the physiologic care model, which emphasizes low-technology strategies and supportive care practices to facilitate childbirth as a biologic process (Goer & Romano, 2012). This movement is continually growing. According to Listening to Mothers III (2013, p. 34), the third national U.S. Survey of hospitalized women's childbearing experiences, 59% of 2400 women stated that "birth should not be interfered with unless medically necessary;" however, 67% of these women had an epidural, 62% an intravenous catheter, 51% one or more vaginal exams, 47% bladder catheters, 31% augmentation with oxytocin during labor, and 20% amniotomy. Only 17% achieved a physiologic/unmedicated birth (2013). What is the reason for this? Is it lack of resources, lack of knowledge, lack of drive, or is it something else?

Without the previous experience of birth, first time mothers who are seeking information may feel lost trying to navigate through all of the available books and classes. Many women will attend hospital-offered classes because they are convenient and a known resource. Although informative, few hospital-based classes truly prepare a woman for physiologic childbirth (Simkin & Bolding, 2004). The limitation of this type of preparation is the rationale for the development of specific, specialized classes that are meant to guide women through the natural progression of labor and birth. In striving for

a successful physiologic birth, women may wonder which natural childbirth education method is best for them.

To determine the options available to women who desire a physiologic birth, a search was done late in 2013 on Google of “natural childbirth education.” This search determined that the top three class types were the Bradley Method®, Lamaze, and HypnoBirthing®. Lamaze has already been studied in depth, so it was decided to investigate HypnoBirthing (The Mongan Method) and the Bradley Method. In this project, I explored the similarities and differences between the two programs and discussed success rates (or childbirth outcomes). To achieve this goal, a scholarly literature review was done using PubMed, ESCO, and CINAHL by searching the following terms: physiologic birth, unmedicated birth, natural birth, Bradley Method, Hypnobirthing, Mongan Method, husband coached childbirth, and childbirth classes. This may aid midwives and childbirth educators as they assist women who wish to have a physiologic or natural childbirth and are seeking childbirth preparation.

Framework

At the present time, physiologic childbirth is an experience for a minority of women in the United States (American College of Nurse-Midwives, 2012). Obstetrical interventions have become the norm. One of the main contributors to this is the use of synthetic oxytocin in more than half of all pregnant women to induce or augment labor. This requires extra interventions to monitor, prevent, and treat possible side effects. In the U.S., 31% of women will give birth by cesarean birth (Declercq, Sakala, Corry, Applebaum, & Herrlich, 2013). Cesarean births do not come without risk and have the potential for serious short and long-term consequences. “Maternal consequences include

postoperative infections, chronic pain, future cesarean births, and placental complications resulting in hemorrhage, hysterectomy, and sometimes death. Adverse infant outcomes include respiratory distress.” (American College of Nurse-Midwives, 2012, p. 530)

In 2010, 98.8% of U.S. women gave birth in hospitals (Martin, Hamilton, Ventura, Osterman, Wilson, & Mathews, 2012) and received a variety of medications- from intravenous narcotics to epidural infusions, and procedures such as continuous fetal monitoring and amniotomy (Declercq et al., 2013; Romano & Lothian, 2008) In addition to being associated with more procedures, hospital-based childbirth is associated with mobility limitations for pregnant women . The ability to move freely in labor has been shown to increase uterine contractility, enhance comfort, reduce need for pharmacologic pain relief, diminish length of labors, and decrease the risk of an operative delivery (Romano & Lothian, 2008). Despite this, only 40% of women having hospital childbirth experiences were allowed to change position or use movement during labor (Declercq et al., 2013).

Specific statistics on how many women in the United States desire a physiologic or natural birth is unknown. However, it is known through the Listening to Mothers III survey (2013) that 17% of hospitalized women bearing single babies achieved a physiologic birth, so the desire is evident . Figure 1 demonstrates that the aspiration for a physiologic birth may be from the belief that labor and birth is a natural healthy process or is a way of being in control; it may also result from a desire for a safe passage for babies or additional personal beliefs (Fleming & Vandermause, 2011; Hardin & Buckner, 2004).

In any case women seek assistance to achieve a physiologic birth. Most women will turn to some form of child birth classes (Declercq et al., 2013). There are several options available (Walker, Visger, & Rossie, 2009), as seen in Figure 1; currently two of the most popular are Hypnobirthing and the Bradley Method. Although both methods were developed to assist women in finding natural and internal ways of coping with the pain of labor, there are distinct similarities and differences between the two programs.

Project Goals

The goal of my Doctorate of Nursing Practice project was to write a manuscript for submission to The *Journal of Perinatal Education* or *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*. In the manuscript, I compared and contrasted two forms of childbirth education, Hypnobirthing (The Mongan Method) and Bradley Method (husband-coached natural childbirth), on program format and content, and on published outcomes from women who have participated in each method.

Figure 1. Framework for choosing a childbirth class to achieve an unmedicated birth

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The numbers of women who desire physiologic birth is unknown. Authors from one study of Norwegian women stated that 72% desire “*as natural a birth as possible*” (Kringeland, Kjersti, Daltveit, & Møller, 2010, p. 26). Authors of a grounded theory study of 36 Canadian women (Jimenez, Klein, Hivon, & Mason, 2010) reported that women’s attitudes, beliefs, and expectations vary significantly when it comes to childbirth. Based on this, Jimenez et al. concluded that each woman perceives birth one of two ways, as a medical condition with risks or as a normal, natural process. They noted that a woman’s perceptions will lead her to different types of obstetrical providers, but often the questioning or search for knowledge will stop there. These authors also found that few women wanted to make decisions about childbirth and stated, “At such a vulnerable time in their lives, many women want to believe that the [provider] knows best and that the medical model of care will ensure a safe outcome” (Jimenez et al., 2010, p. 162). These results make it likely that women’s true desires of birth are not being discussed and that the norm or status quo of the medicalization of childbirth is influencing the process.

Specific statistics on how many women in the United States desire a physiologic or natural birth are unavailable. However in 2006, 56% of first time mothers took childbirth classes, and 36% of these women stated that the reason for taking the classes was to help manage labor pain (Declercq et al., 2006). In the most recent Listening to Mothers Survey (2013), which surveyed U.S. women who gave birth in a hospital during 2011-12, the number of first time mothers taking childbirth classes was 59%. In 2013, the percentage of U.S. women achieving a physiologic/unmedicated birth rose from 14% in

2006 (Survey II) to 17% in 2013. Listening to Mothers III findings (2013) substantiated a correlation between women taking childbirth classes and the use of non-medication techniques for managing pain. It appears that the number of women achieving physiologic birth is increasing in the U.S. but it is unknown how many American women would prefer a physiologic birth or as the Norwegian women stated it, as natural a birth as possible (Kringeland et al., 2010). Even with the large percentage of women taking childbirth classes and the increasing physiologic birth rates, the majority of women giving birth in the U.S. will have some form of pain medication in labor and almost three quarters will have an epidural (Listening to Mothers III, 2013). In a study of childbirth outcomes in 33 women who desired an unmedicated birth, Carlton, Callister, and Stoneman (2005), discovered that “intense pain, length of labor, exhaustion, not knowing what to expect coupled with a sense of anxiety, feelings of lack of control and poor preparation, and the inability to relax were mentioned as the most common reasons for changing their birth plan” (p. 148). Although it cannot be concluded that childbirth classes alone will decrease the use of epidurals in labor (Simkin & Bolding, 2004), many of the reasons for not succeeding in natural birth mentioned by Carlton et al.’s sample may be topics addressed in these classes.

Many websites and journal articles discuss the respective philosophies of Bradley Method and Hypnobirthing, but few studies have looked at the success rates (e.g., numbers of unmedicated births) of these programs. Two publications were found that included objective results from women who used the Bradley Method. An in depth synthesis of these can be found in Appendix C, Table 1. The earliest article included findings from a childbirth instructor’s statistics as she reported them (Bradley, 1995); the

second included data from a qualitative study of 16 women stating the self-reported outcomes of their births (Monto, 1996). Lisa Bradley (1995) reported that she had taught 65 couples using the Bradley Method and her outcomes included a vaginal birth rate of 89.3% with only 3% of these women using pain medication. She did not state whether the pain medication received was an epidural or intravenous narcotics. In Monto (1996), four series of Bradley Method classes were systematically observed. Of the 16 women in the study, eight had an unmedicated birth and four had cesarean births.

Studies specifically evaluating Hypnobirthing were not found, but five published studies, which included two systematic reviews, and one unpublished thesis, evaluated outcomes of hypnosis in laboring women (Cyna, 2011; Cyna, Andrew, & McAuliffe, 2006; Cyna, McAuliffe, & Andrew, 2004; Fisher, Esplin, Stoddard, & Silver, 2009; Huntley, Coon, & Ernst, 2004; Madden, Middleton, Cyna, Matthewson, & Jones, 2012). An in depth synthesis of these articles can be found in Appendix C, Table 2. Cyna et al. (2006) taught pregnant women in Australia to use self-hypnosis as adjunctive analgesia during labor. Up to four different teaching sessions were done that lasted between 40 and 60 minutes. Women self-selected to the hypnosis group, normally due to their reported general interest in hypnosis in hopes to avoid an epidural. Investigators reported a significant difference between epidural rates in the hypnosis group (36%) compared with the control group (53%) among primiparas ($p < .05$), but not among multiparous women. Although Cyna and colleagues did not specifically use Hypnobirthing, Hypnobirthing's class structure is set up similarly to the program described, with five class sessions and self-hypnosis being taught throughout (Mongan, 2005).

Madden et al. (2012), in their Cochrane review of seven randomized control trials that included 1213 women, found no significant difference between the hypnosis and control groups on pharmacological pain relief, spontaneous vaginal birth, satisfaction with pain relief, sense of coping with labor, satisfaction with childbirth experience, infant admissions to neonatal intensive care unit, and breastfeeding rates at hospital discharge. However, they did identify benefits to hypnosis: significantly decreased lengths of labor, maternal hospital stay times, and labor pain intensity. Because of the heterogeneity of the studies, these authors had reservations on giving a recommendation on hypnosis for labor. Madden et al. conclude that “although the intervention shows some promise, further research is needed before recommendations can be made regarding its clinical usefulness for pain management in maternity care” (2012, p. 21).

Two substantial gaps have been identified in determining the effects of the Bradley Method and Hypnobirthing on physiologic birth. The first is the lack of information delineating how many U.S. women truly desire a physiologic birth. The second is that current evidence makes it difficult to determine whether either the Bradley Method or Hypnobirthing will help women who desire this type of birth to achieve it.

METHODS

For this doctoral project, I have collected published evidence on natural/unmedicated birth, birth plans, Hypnobirthing, Bradley Method, and pain management in labor; read *HypnoBirthing The Mongan Method* (Mongan, 2005), *Husband-Coached Childbirth* (Bradley, 1996), and The Bradley Method student workbook (Hathaway, Hathaway, & Hathaway, 2012); attended both a series of Bradley Method classes and HypnoBirthing classes at a Southern California Birth Center; and developed a table comparing Hypnobirthing and Bradley Method programs and outcomes; and written a manuscript using the chosen journal's author guidelines.

Ethics

As part of my Doctorate of Nursing Practice project, I applied to the Institutional Review Board of California State University, Fullerton in order to observe locally available classes of both the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing and was granted an exempt status.

Publication

The journal that I am submitting my manuscript to is *The Journal of Perinatal Education* (JPE), a peer-reviewed journal that “focuses on pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum, breastfeeding, neonatal care, early parenting, and young family development” (*Journal of Perinatal Education*, 2012). This journal is specifically for childbirth educators, so its mission is to publish evidence-based articles to increase the knowledge of educators and other healthcare professionals “that will improve practice and efforts to support safe, healthy birth” (*Journal of Perinatal Education*, 2012). Readers of *JPE* include childbirth educators, nurses, midwives, and physicians

RESULTS – PROJECT MANUSCRIPT

The manuscript submitted to *Journal of Perinatal Education* can be found in Appendix A, and the guidelines for authors from *JPE* can be found in Appendix B

DISCUSSION

Based on the literature reviewed, differences between the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing in regards to curricula and philosophy were identified. Although the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing are both forms of natural childbirth education, women taught with each receive very different experiences. The Bradley Method involves a longer set of classes that are intended to educate on multiple components of pregnancy, labor, birth, and postpartum. Class content includes ways to stay healthy in pregnancy as well as dangers in pregnancy and dangers of medication use in labor. HypnoBirthing does not include “danger” elements in its curriculum due to the philosophy that discussing certain dangers will cause fear of pregnancy/childbirth for some women instead of the intended goal of education (Mongan, 2005). HypnoBirthing focuses mainly on relaxation for self-hypnosis, the natural birth process, and releasing fears related to pregnancy and childbirth. The differences between the two methods continue to the core of their management of pain during childbirth. With the Bradley Method, women are taught to help relax to get through labor with the support of a “coach.” In HypnoBirthing, women are taught self-hypnosis to control the degree and manner in which they feel the contractions of labor and the process of birth; a support person is encouraged to be with the woman in classes and during labor, but this is not a requirement for participation in HypnoBirthing.

If published, the manuscript can be used by women’s health providers and educators to educate women on the differences between the two methods. By using the tables in the article as patient teaching tools, content can be presented to prospective

parents in a format that readily displays the similarities and differences of the Bradley Method and Hypnobirthing.

Although a discussion of the published outcomes of the two methods was presented in the manuscript, this topic would be more difficult to relate to clients because of the limited data available. In my own practice I would discuss that, although evidence has shown hypnosis to be helpful with increasing the rate of vaginal births without the use of epidural and decreasing pain intensity, time in active labor, and days spent in the hospital, no studies specifically have been done on HypnoBirthing. The research on the success rates of both Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing is extremely limited and it is important that each woman decides which opinion is the best fit for her.

This project has been a starting point to investigate two popular childbirth education philosophies and their impact on physiologic birth in the United States. A next step could be a pilot study to evaluate the numbers of women in the U.S. who desire a physiologic birth, followed by studies of the birth outcomes of different childbirth education methods. In conclusion, the absolute effects of attending childbirth classes such as Hypnobirthing or Bradley method are not known. However, when women are empowered to learn about birth and their capacity for physiologic birth, then “pregnancy and childbirth [will be] healthy, normal experiences for the vast majority of women and their babies” (Goer & Romano, 2012, p. 2).

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APPENDIX A

MANUSCRIPT SUBMITTED TO *JOURNAL OF PERINATAL EDUCATION*

Comparison of the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing Childbirth Education Classes

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Comparison of the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing Childbirth Education Classes

Background

In the last century, birth in the United States has been taken from a natural process in most women's lives to a medicalized procedure similar to one of disease management with multiple "interventions" (Hinote & Wasserman, 2012; Romano & Lothian, 2008). Since the 1960s, a small group of women and providers have tried to restore the ownership of birth to women by supporting the physiologic care model, which emphasizes low-technology strategies and supportive care practices to facilitate childbirth as a biologic process (Goer & Romano, 2012). This movement is growing. According to Listening to Mothers (LTM) III (2013, p. 34), the third national U.S. Survey of 2400 hospitalized women's childbearing experiences, 59% of women stated that "birth should not be interfered with unless medically necessary;" however, 67% of these women received an epidural, 62% an intravenous catheter, 51% one or more vaginal exams, 47% bladder catheters, 31% augmentation with oxytocin during labor, and 20% amniotomy. In fact, only 17% of women surveyed achieved a physiologic or unmedicated birth (Declercq, Sakala, Corry, Applebaum, & Herrlich, 2013). With such a large gap between the desired and the achieved, are we as providers and childbirth educators doing all that we can to help these women obtain their goal?

With 99% of U.S. women giving birth in hospitals (Martin et al., 2012), many providers recommend that their pregnant clients attend classes offered by the hospital at which they deliver. This may not be best for women who desire a natural birth. Although informative, few hospital-based classes truly prepare a woman for physiologic childbirth (Simkin & Bolding, 2004). For this and other reasons, outside of hospital-classes have

been developed that specialize in guiding women through the natural progression of labor and birth. In order for providers and childbirth educators to best meet women's needs, they must be knowledgeable on the content and outcomes of such classes.

To determine availability of information for parents, providers and childbirth educators in the most relevant natural methods, a Google search of “natural childbirth education” was done. The most common class types found were the Bradley Method, Lamaze, and HypnoBirthing. Lamaze has been studied in depth and is what most hospital based classes were developed from (Monto, 1996; Walker et al., 2009), so will not be included in this analysis. The purpose of this article is to explore the similarities and differences between the Bradley Method® and HypnoBirthing® methods and to discuss published outcomes of these two programs to allow providers and childbirth educators to be more comfortable discussing them with their clients. To achieve this goal, a scholarly literature review was done using PubMed, ESCO, and CINAHL by searching the following terms: physiologic birth, unmedicated birth, natural birth, Bradley Method, Hypnobirthing, Mongan Method, husband coached childbirth, and childbirth classes.

Historical Perspective

History of the Bradley Method

According to the American Academy of Husband-Coached Childbirth (AAHCC) website, the purpose of the Bradley Method® is to teach “natural childbirth and view birth as a natural process. It is [their] belief that most women with proper education, preparation, and the help of a loving and supportive coach can be taught to give birth naturally” (bradleymethod.com). Dr. Robert Bradley, an obstetrician/gynecologist, developed the method in 1947 as a result of his objection to artificial conditions in the

hospitals at this time. Dr. Bradley grew up on a farm in Nebraska and was accustomed to seeing the natural process that animals went through to give birth. He believed that humans could be taught to give birth without pain and fear (Bradley, 2008).

Dr. Bradley believed certain conditions were essential for a laboring woman: darkness, solitude, quiet, physical comfort during the first stage of labor, physical relaxation, controlled breathing, and need for closed eyes/appearance of sleep. He espoused the fundamental premise that the laboring women would have a supportive coach/husband in this process (Walker, Visger, & Rossie, 2009).

History of HypnoBirthing

HypnoBirthing (The Mongan Method) was developed by Marie Mongan and was first described in her book *HypnoBirthing -- A Celebration of Life* (1989). The ideas behind this method of childbirth education started with Mongan's own childbirth experiences. Inspired by Dr. Grantly Dick-Read's book, *Childbirth without Fear* (1942), Mongan honed her self-hypnosis skills (hypnobirthing.com). The major tenet of the HypnoBirthing philosophy is "the belief that every woman has within her the power to call upon her natural maternal instinct to birth her babies in joy and comfort in a manner that most mirrors nature" (Mongan, 2005).

HypnoBirthing preparation aims to have expectant mothers view birth in a positive manner with the belief that childbirth does not have to be painful. It is not meant to teach coping methods, but instead focuses on teaching the skills of deep relaxation, visualization, and self-hypnosis (Walker et al., 2009).

Comparison of Curricula

The objectives of both HypnoBirthing and the Bradley Method are to help women to achieve a physiological birth. Summaries of curricula or course content from both programs were found on the HypnoBirthing and AAHCC websites. A curricular comparison can be found in Tables 1 and 2, which cover course content and recommended time to cover different content areas.

Published Outcomes from Participants in HypnoBirthing and the Bradley Method

Classes

According to the AAHCC website, over 86% of the women who used the Bradley Method nationwide achieved a spontaneous, unmedicated vaginal birth (bradleymethod.com). Several attempts through email and phone messages to the international headquarter in Sherman Oaks, California, were made to discuss with the AAHCC how this number was obtained, but no response was received. Several Bradley instructors reported that these statistics are compiled from the self-report of clients to their instructors or the AAHCC website.

In 2010, the HypnoBirthing Institute compared data from Listening to Mothers II (LTM II) Report, the United States Division of Vital Statistics birth data for 2007 (Martin et al., 2010) and 2001 HypnoBirthing Parents' Birth reports that were collected between October 2005 and October 2010 (hypnobirthing.com). These results were posted on the HypnoBirthing website. During this period, approximately 20% of HypnoBirthing mothers reported having an epidural and less than 10% intramuscular or intravenous analgesia which contrasts with LTM II (2006), 76% of women received an epidural and 22% used some form of narcotics. Also reported was the fact that HypnoBirthing mothers

had a 17% cesarean birth rate compared to the LTM II rate of 32% and the United States Division of Vital Statistics (Martin et al., 2012) rate of 31.8%.

Multiple studies have been conducted on hypnosis in childbirth but none were found that evaluated outcomes of women taught the HypnoBirthing curriculum. In a Cochrane systematic review on hypnosis as pain management in labor and delivery, authors concluded that women in the hypnosis intervention had less pain, decreased time in active labor, and fewer days in the hospital, but this was dependent on the training being done in the first or second trimesters and that four or more classes were attended (Madden, Middleton, Cyna, Matthewson, & Jones, 2012). Of the studies reviewed, that done by Cyna, Andrew, and McAuliffe (2006) evaluated a hypnosis intervention that most closely resembled the HypnoBirthing method. Cyna and colleagues found that women who used hypnosis had greater numbers of spontaneous vaginal births without the use of an epidural than did women who self-selected not to use hypnosis.

Although no published studies discussing the success of the method could be found on the effectiveness of the Bradley Method, two articles, both peer-reviewed, were identified. In the first, a birthing instructor discusses her own statistics for women she had trained (Bradley, 1995), and in the second, results are given from 16 couples who participated in four different classes of the Bradley Method with different instructors (Monto, 1996). An outcomes comparison on the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing can be found in Table 3.

Conclusion/Discussion

Although the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing are both forms of natural childbirth education, women taught with each receive very different experiences. The

Bradley Method involves a set of more classes that are in the aggregate, intended to educate on multiple components of pregnancy, labor, birth, and postpartum. Class content includes ways to stay healthy in pregnancy as well as dangers in pregnancy and dangers of medication use in labor. In contrast, HypnoBirthing classes do not include discussion on dangers in pregnancy, medication use, complications, or cesarean birth in the curriculum based on the stated philosophy that discussing certain dangers will cause fear of pregnancy/childbirth for some women instead of the intended goal of education (Mongan, 2005). HypnoBirthing focuses primarily on relaxation for self-hypnosis, the natural birth process, and releasing fears related to pregnancy and childbirth.

Differences between the two methods continue to the core of their management of pain during childbirth. With the Bradley Method, women are taught relaxation exercises to help endure labor. The “coach” is the woman’s main support to aid her in achieving a physiologic birth and to help to keep outside factors from interfering with the process. The coach has an integral role in the success of the method. In contrast, women choosing HypnoBirthing are taught *self*-hypnosis to enable them to control the degree and manner in which they feel labor contractions and the process of birth. A support person is encouraged to be with women in the classes and during labor, but this is not a requirement for HypnoBirthing participation.

This review has delineated the similarities and differences between the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing in regards to curricula and philosophy. The content can be used by providers of women’s health and health educators in discussions with prospective parents about the two methods. It may also be useful for faculty who teach obstetric

courses as nursing students would benefit from understanding commonalities and unique aspects of these childbirth methods.

Tables 1 and 2 can be used as references for providers to guide their patients to methods that suit their childbirth situations. Table 1 compares the overall foci in each of the methods. For the woman whose partner desires a more active or guiding role during the birth, it is evident that the theme of birth coach in the Bradley method (discussed in 40% of the classes) will likely resonate with both a woman and her partner. Conversely, a woman who does not have partner support or whose partner is interested in supporting but not becoming the women's spokes person during birth, may benefit from Hypnobirthing as she mobilizes her own inner strength through hypnosis and relaxation (in 80% of the classes) for the birth process. Women who have also experienced bonding difficulties, prior traumatic birth experiences, or have fear in general related to birth may benefit from the bonding/parenting and releasing fear (discussed in 40% of classes) content in Hypnobirthing. For couples who believe that being educated on interventions such as medication use and hospital procedures will assist them to avoid such interventions, they may benefit from this content being covered in the Bradley Method.

Table 2 shows specific content areas addressed in each of the classes. One can see that the number of classes in the Bradley Method is greater than HypnoBirthing, leading to a greater time commitment. For a woman who is expressing interest in classes in the first or second trimester, the Bradley Method is an option. For a woman who may not have considered classes before the third trimester, it may not be an option due to the time needed for completion. Table 2 also shows that HypnoBirthing focuses on positive thoughts, releasing of fear, education on the natural birth process, self-hypnosis, and

relaxation. The Bradley Method covers a much wider spectrum of topics, such as importance of staying low risk, nutrition, exercise, anatomy and physiology of pregnancy, labor, and birth, choices for labor and birth, coach's role, medication use, informed consent, complications, and cesarean birth. It would be important to discuss with a woman and her partner the reasons for wanting to take a natural childbirth class and what they hope to gain.

The paucity of evidence on the two methods does not support provider recommendation of one method over the other with regards to outcomes, as can be seen in Table 3. To date, there are no well-designed studies of the Bradley Method and the data that is available is based on self-reported outcomes. Although there is higher level of evidence for the use of hypnosis in general for pain management in labor, it is important to note that for both HypnoBirthing and Bradley Method, only lower levels of evidence are available. The lack of substantive outcome data compels the need for providers to discuss that choice of childbirth education method does not guarantee a physiologic birth. Further study is needed; for example, a study is warranted comparing birth outcomes from the different natural childbirth education methods that includes only women who desire a physiological birth and who are giving birth in settings that will support rather than counter their preferences for physiologic birth. For women to continue to try to reclaim ownership of birth through the physiologic care model, there needs to be an available avenue for them to learn about optimization of this personal outcome. Healthcare providers and educators can educate these women about specifics of the Bradley Method and HypnoBirthing as two different pathways to guide them through the natural process of labor and birth.

Table 1

*Comparison of Time Spent on Main Points of HypnoBirthing and the Bradley Method**Curricula*

Main point topics	% of classes discussing topic for HypnoBirthing	% of classes discussing for the Bradley Method
Education	60	56
Relaxation	80 ^a	24 ^b
Birth companion or coach	20	40
Natural birth instincts or process of natural pregnancy & birth	60	32
Birth planning	20	8
Bonding with baby/parenting	40	8
Dangers of medication/drug use in pregnancy & birth	0	16
Releasing fear	40	0
Importance of staying healthy & low risk	0	8
Nutrition	0	8

Note. Adapted from “Course Content” by American Academy of Husband-Coached Childbirth. (2013). <http://www.bradleymethod.com> & “Childbirth classes for gentle birthing” by HypnoBirthing Institute (2013). <http://www.hypnobirthing.com>.

^a Referred to as Relaxation & Self-Hypnosis. ^b Referred to as Relaxation Technique.

Table 2

Comparison of Class Content

Class #	HypnoBirthing® class topics	Synthesis of HypnoBirthing	The Bradley Method® class topics	Synthesis of the Bradley Method
1	Building A Positive Expectancy Introduction to HypnoBirthing® philosophy History of birthing Having an easier, more comfortable, & safer birthing experience How nature perfectly designed women's bodies to birth How to assist, rather than resist, natural birthing instincts Vocabulary for calm & gentle birthing Viewing birthing videos to facilitate visualizing gentle births	History of birthing Nature's design Natural birthing Instincts Calm vocabulary Videos	Introduction to the Bradley Method History of The Bradley Method®, its philosophy and goals. Getting to know instructors and class members Healthy behaviors for pregnant women Important pregnancy exercises Discussion of how to handle pain How to avoid unnecessary pain in labor.	Importance of staying healthy & low risk Exercises Relaxation
2	Falling in Love with Your Baby/Preparing Mind & Body Mind of newborn baby Prenatal bonding techniques Self-relaxation, breathing & deepening techniques Hypnotic relaxation & visualization Care provider selection Birth companion's role Preparing your body with massage & toning	Prenatal bonding Self-relaxation Techniques Massage & toning Techniques Provider selection Birth companion's role	Nutrition in Pregnancy Good nutrition Understanding important nutrients for pregnancy Evaluation & improvement of diet Review pregnancy exercises Discussion of sex, breastfeeding and importance of staying low risk and healthy	Nutrition Staying healthy & low risk
3	Getting Ready to Welcome your Baby Preparing a Birthing Preference Sheet Preparing the body for birthing Light touch labor massage Your body working for/with you	Birth Plans Relaxation techniques Avoiding artificial induction Releasing negative	Pregnancy Changes in the body during pregnancy Anatomy & physiology Natural ways to handle common pregnancy discomforts	Anatomy & physiology of pregnancy Common discomforts Coaching challenges Choices for labor & birth

	Avoiding artificial induction Releasing negative emotions, fears & limiting thoughts.	emotions & fears to work with and assist the natural birth instincts Fear causes pain	Coaches understanding changes and discomforts Choices in labor & birth	
4	An overview of Birthing – A Labor of Love Onset of labor Thinning and opening phase Birth explained simply Settling in at chosen birth place Preparing for baby’s birth Passing time through labor Hallmarks of labor What to do if labor rests or slows Companion’s prompts and activities Birthing with your baby Protecting the natural birthing experience Birth rehearsal imagery	Anatomy and physiology of birth Birth settings Activities to walk through birth experience Self-relaxation activities	The Coach's Role Focus on pregnancy & birth from coach’s point of view in regards to coaching during pregnancy, importance of natural childbirth, bonding, and father’s role in breastfeeding Conclusion of staying low risk in pregnancy Discuss drugs, myths, and birthing	Coach’s Role Discussion on drugs, myths & birth Staying healthy & low risk (3 of 3)
5	Birth – Breathing Love - Bringing Life Moving into birthing Positions for descent and birthing Breathing baby down to birth Baby moves to the breast Family bonding with your baby	Relaxation techniques Birthing techniques Breastfeeding Bonding	Introduction to First Stage Labor Anatomy & physiology of first stage of labor Importance of natural process Natural safeguards Basic coaching techniques & how to practice Standard hospital admission and prepping procedures	Anatomy & physiology of first stage of labor Overview of labor and birth as natural process Assistant coaches
6			Introduction to Second Stage Labor Anatomy & physiology of second stage of labor Importance of natural process Natural safeguards	Anatomy and physiology of second stage of labor Transition

	Discuss natural alignment plateau & fetal Heimlich maneuver Basic pushing & positions Discussion on coach's role Third Stage	Pushing technique's and second stage positions Natural process Third Stage
7	Planning Your Birth How to make a birth plan Discussion on what choices available, importance of evaluating one's feelings, listing priorities, and meeting with medical team to discuss choices in a positive way First stage labor rehearsal in class	Birth Plan Informed consent Evaluation of feelings
8	Variations and Complications / Postpartum Preparation Various complications Discussion on how to avoid if possible, evaluate whether necessary to intervene, and how to handle interventions that become necessary Postpartum care for mother and baby	Complications of labor & birth Cesarean delivery Post partum care
9	Advanced First Stage Techniques Advanced coaching techniques for first stage of labor First stage guide Labor rehearsal and role playing	First stage relaxation techniques and practicing
10	Advanced Second Stage Techniques Advanced labor rehearsal Second stage study guide	Second stage relaxation techniques and practicing Coach's role
11	Being a Great Coach / Are You Ready? B.E.S.T. techniques for labor and birth review Discussion for coaches how to handle challenges in labor Emergency childbirth	Coach's role Bradley Energy Saving Techniques (BEST) Emergency childbirth Activity on what is labor

	Discussion on the theory of "what is labor" and why it is so different for each woman and even for each pregnancy	and differences for each woman
12	Preparing for Your New Family Advanced labor rehearsal Discussion on newborn care, mothering, fathering, breastfeeding, how to handle a crying baby, and adjusting to the many changes	Newborn Information Breastfeeding Parenting Adjustments to the family

Note. Adapted from “Course Content” by American Academy of Husband-Coached Childbirth. (2013). <http://www.bradleymethod.com> & “Childbirth classes for gentle birthing” by HypnoBirthing Institute (2013). <http://www.hypnobirthing.com>.

Table 3

*Evidence of Outcomes from HypnoBirthing and the Bradley Methods of Childbirth**Education*

Published Studies	Outcomes	
	Hypnobirthing	Bradley Method
Comparison of birth outcomes for 77 Australian women who self-selected to receive training in hypnosis (closely mirrored intervention taught in HypnoBirthing) compared with 3249 women who did not; all had hospital births during 2006 (Cyna, Andrew, & McAuliffe, 2006).	Spontaneous vaginal births in women without epidural ($P < .05$): - Nulliparous (46% with hypnosis; 32% control) - Multiparous (67% with hypnosis; 54% control)	
	Spontaneous vaginal births in women with epidural ($P < .05$): - Nulliparous (36% with hypnosis; 53% control) - Multiparous (19% with hypnosis; 29% control)	
Systematic review on hypnosis for pain management during labor & childbirth (Madden, Middleton, Cyna, Matthewson & Jones, 2012)	Differences in favor of women in hypnosis groups ($P < .05$): 1. ↓ pain intensity 2. ↓ time in active labor 3. ↓ number of hospital days	
	Hypnosis training in 1st & 2nd trimester ↓ use of pharmacological pain relief in labor ($RR .42, P < .00001$) but not when training done only in 3rd trimester	
	Hypnosis training with 4 or more classes ↑ rate of spontaneous vaginal births ($RR 1.59, P = .025$) but not < 4 classes	
Other Evidence	Hypnobirthing	Bradley Method
Personal statistics from 65 couples taught by childbirth educator (not author of Bradley Method) (Bradley, 1995)		10.7% cesarean delivery rate 3% pain medication (not specified whether epidural or intravenous)
Report of 16 couples who participated in Bradley Method classes with 4 different instructors (Monto, 1996)		5/6 achieved planned homebirth 8 deliveries without medications 25% cesarean delivery rate

Note. RR = relative risk.

APPENDIX B

AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR *JPE*

The Journal of Perinatal Education

The Official Journal of Lamaze® International

GUIDELINES FOR AUTHORS

The Journal of Perinatal Education (JPE) is the official journal of Lamaze International, whose mission is to promote, support, and protect natural, safe, and healthy birth through education and advocacy.

As the leading peer-reviewed journal specifically for childbirth educators, JPE publishes evidence-based articles to advance the knowledge of aspiring and seasoned educators in any setting—independent or private practice, community, hospital, nursing or midwifery school—and to inform educators and other health-care professionals on research that will improve their practice and their efforts to support safe, healthy birth. The journal also publishes features that provide practical resources and advice health-care professionals can use to enhance the quality and effectiveness of their care or teaching to prepare expectant parents for birth.

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- examples of exemplary maternal-newborn services or clinical projects that translate best evidence into care practices;
- current issues or emerging trends that influence care practices for childbearing families and newborns;

- birth stories and personal experiences of women or families that describe natural, safe, and healthy birth;

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- guest editorials with critical commentary on professional issues or trends influencing maternity care;
 - letters to the editor of 300 words or less, commenting on recent articles published in the journal; and
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APPENDIX C

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Table 1

Bradley Method Studies

Purpose	Design	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations	Notes
To discuss purpose and breakdown of the Bradley method classes (Bradley, 1995)	Informative	n/a	n/a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Staying low-risk - Normal Birth - Intervention - Communications - Provider section - Big gap in research for results for birthing classes 	<p>“Bradley teachers in general find that their students have lower rates of induction, cesareans, pain drugs, episiotomy, IVs, and so on. Bradley students generally have higher rates of breastfeeding and frequently express high satisfaction with their births and the classes- Evidence for this comes from statements made at various gatherings of Bradley teachers, and from results of about 185 births to Bradley class attendees in the Omaha, Nebraska area. Selected statistics were gathered from 1986-1992. Bradley Method headquarters occasionally compiles information from the results cards that Bradley parents and teachers are asked to mail in” (Bradley, Lisa)</p> <p>Instructor stats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taught 65 couples - Cesarean birth rate 10.7% - 89.3% vaginal birth rate (author states 90%) - 3% pain medication (not specified) 	<p>Bradley format</p> <p>Teacher’s own stats with teaching Bradley</p>

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					if epidural or IV) - 64 mothers initially breastfed - 3% induction and augmented - 12 (18%) planned home births (2 transferred) - 8 successful VBACs (2 failed)	
<p>Detailed findings on the experiences of 15 students and teachers of the Bradley Method (McKinney, 2006)</p> <p>Addresses participant's thoughts on classes, praise and criticism of method, and comments on perceived levels of success and empowerment</p>	Qualitative	<p>Participants primarily came from Bradley Method online discussion board</p> <p>United States</p> <p>Done through email</p>	<p>Saturation</p> <p>Shared findings with participants at several points in study for member checks & consulted with colleagues on content and brain-storming ideas</p>	<p>5 Themes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Role of partners - Concept of natural childbirth - Importance of relaxation & preparation - Quality of materials & teachers - Relationships formed with caregivers <p>Subthemes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concepts of teamwork - Control - Self advocacy - Consumerism 	<p>1- Participants defined personal empowerment as the chance to ask questions, having right to accept/refuse routine tx, & to make educated choices</p> <p>2-Liked that method treated birth as a natural occurrence rather than a medical event</p> <p>-Idea that method gave women some form of control over labor was also mentioned several times</p> <p>3- All participants discussed the benefits of relaxation & how it helped with labor</p> <p>4-Some participants thought the materials out of date & poorly assembled. Others criticized how the material glossed over the pain involved in birth. Some teachers perceived problems with the AAHCC in both management & teacher training</p> <p>5- Like the role of a supportive spouse, caregiver's role is a vital one that has consequences on the laboring woman's remembrance & outlook on birth</p>	Helpful article for discussing different personalities for different methods
Differences between Lamaze &	Qualitative Interviews	Four series of Bradley classes in 1992	N/A	Delivered Unmedicated: 8 Bradley 2 women in Lamaze	- Bradley mentioned as "antimedical" and more "rigid" by Lamaze instructors	

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Bradley (Monto, 1996) Perspective on women's personalities	done 3 times - Early in series of classes - Last day of class - 4-10 weeks after delivery	were systematically observed 16 women Bradley (6 women interviewed from Bradley class by lay midwife/ planned homebirths) 15 women Lamaze 1st time mothers 2- private residence 1- doctor's office 1- private hospital		Delivered by Cesarean: 4 Bradley 7 Lamaze	- Bradley instructors interpreted medicine's hx of "unnecessary & harmful intervention as a reason to question many of the contemporary medical interventions in childbirth." - Bradley instructors supported midwives & unconventional birth - Bradley instructors all conveyed disapproval for medical intervention & knowledge that most intervention is not needed "Those enrolled in Bradley classes were more likely to plan unmedicated or out-of-hospital births, were much more critical of the medical birth model, and were less likely to use pain medication or have cesarean deliveries than women enrolled in Lamaze classes" (Monto, 1996)	

Note. Tx = Treatment; AAHCC = American Academy of Husband Coached Childbirth; Hx = history; IV = intravenous catheter; N/A = not applicable; VBACs = vaginal birth after cesarean.

Table 2

Hypnosis Studies

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations	Notes
<p>Primary: To assess whether antenatal hypnosis is effective in reducing use of pain medication, incidence of adverse outcomes on mothers and babies, and impacts mother's emotional well being (Cyna, 2011)</p> <p>Secondary: Compare two methods of delivering antenatal hypnosis</p>	<p>RCT into groups</p> <p>Self-referral into study</p> <p>Double blind</p> <p>Groups 1 & 2 attended 3 classes and CD listened to daily</p> <p># of participants Group 1: 154 Group 2: 143 Group 3: 151</p>	<p>Largest tertiary maternity unit in South Australia</p> <p>Women > 34 weeks gestation</p> <p>Singleton Viable fetus</p> <p>Vertex presentation who are not in active labor</p> <p>Planning vaginal birth</p> <p>Excluded if had previous hypnosis preparation, poor understanding of English, already enrolled in different pregnancy trial, active psychological</p>	<p>3 groups</p> <p>-Hypnosis administered by hypnotherapist plus audio CD on hypnosis for reinforcement & consolidation</p> <p>-Audio CD on hypnosis administered by a nurse without training in hypnotherapy</p> <p>-No intervention control; participants were asked to continue with their usual preparation for childbirth</p>	<p>Less than 50% of women in groups 1 & 2 attended all 3 classes</p> <p>26.0% of Group 1 & 30.8% of Group 2 complied with all parts of intervention</p> <p>15.6% of group 1 & 12.6% of group 2 attended zero sessions</p> <p>No difference between pain medication use: Group 1: 81.2% Group 2: 76.9% Group 3: 76.2%</p> <p>No difference found for: Oxytocin labor augmentation Incidence of spontaneous vaginal birth</p> <p>Increased induction rate in Hypnosis Group (40.9% to 31.1%)</p> <p>No differences between groups on mode of delivery, incidence of episiotomy, need for blood transfusion,</p>	<p>No statistical differences found except that more women in Hypnosis group needed to be induced</p> <p>Women who were induced needed more pain medications</p> <p>Sub-group note: Women who did yoga in pregnancy & did hypnosis- used less analgesia than women who did not use yoga & were in hypnosis group (70.8% to 88.8%, $p = .01$)</p> <p>No difference was noted between the participated that went to all 3 sessions and those that did not in the use of analgesia</p> <p>Failure of hypnosis intervention by be due to selection bias, # of sessions & timing, tertiary setting, & effects of increased incidence of induction on women allocated to hypnosis group of study</p> <p>Only 10.9% of women did not</p>	

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		<p>or psychiatric problems, or pain caused by pathological entities</p> <p>Enrolled during attendance at antenatal clinic, classes, midwifery group practice, or inpatient</p>		<p>length of stay in hospital, breastfeeding</p> <p>No difference in mother's perceiving that she received adequate pain relief, maternal perceptions of birth being better than expected or a positive experience, meconium staining or Apgars of < 7, postpartum anxiety or depression scores, maternal readmission to hospital, incidence of baby readmissions, and whether baby was settled</p> <p>Nearly 50% of women in intervention groups believed that hypnosis was helpful during birth</p>	<p>have some college</p> <p>Previous studies show beneficial when six or more session & administered before third trimester</p>	
<p>Systematic Review of hypnosis for pain relief in labor & childbirth (Cyna, McAuliffe, & Andrew, 2004)</p>	<p>Review of 5 RCT & 14 NRC</p> <p>Only 4 RTC & 2 NRC studies were included due to criteria</p>	<p>Studies between 1969-2001</p> <p>224 Women from RTC</p> <p>878 Women from NRC</p>	<p>Primary outcome measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of Analgesia & pain scores <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Duration of labor - Labor augmentation - Mode of 	<p>Freeman Trial:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failed to show difference in epidural use - Pts rated having good or moderate response to hypnosis have fewer epidurals - Longer 1st stage of labor for hypnosis <p>2 of the NRC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in median pain scores & decreased analgesia requirements 	<p>Reasons for Hypnosis reducing analgesia requirements in labor:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Teaching hypnosis facilitates pt autonomy & sense of control" - Majority of people are likely to be able to use, reducing apprehension - Reduction of medication augmentation may minimize hyperstimulation <p>Internal Validity of studies: inadequate random allocation,</p>	<p>Hypnotherapy defined "as the clinical use of suggestions during hypnosis to achieve specific therapeutic goals such as the alleviation of pain or anxiety"</p>

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			Delivery	<p>Harmon & Jenkins: - Decrease in length of 1st stage of labor for hypnosis</p> <p>Harman: - Reduction in use of oxytocin for augmentation for hypnosis - Increased NSVDs with hypnosis</p>	<p>concealment, or lack of blinding</p> <p>External Validity: Only Freeman looked at whether epidural analgesia use is affected by hypnosis. Epidural service on demand in most L&D units</p>	
<p>Prospectively collect data related to the use of hypnosis in clinical practice (Cyna, Andrew, & McAuliffe 2006)</p> <p>Compare birth outcomes of women taught self-hypnosis with gestational age and parity matched controls, delivering after 37 wks</p>	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>Done during 2003</p> <p>Women taught up to 4 occasions between 40-60 minutes after 35 weeks</p>	<p>Women's & Children's Hospital in South Australia</p> <p>77 women in hypnosis group</p> <p>3249 women in control group</p>	<p>Self hypnosis reviewed</p> <p>Epidural analgesia/spinal</p> <p>Augmentation</p> <p>Mode of delivery</p>	<p>Significant difference of $P < .05$ between:</p> <p>No epidural</p> <p>Nulliparous 46% with hypnosis 32% control</p> <p>Multiparous 67% with hypnosis 54% control</p> <p>Epidural</p> <p>Nulliparous 36% with hypnosis 53% control</p> <p>Multiparous 19% hypnosis 29%control</p> <p>Epidural/augmentation</p> <p>Nulliparous 12% hypnosis 30% control</p> <p>Multiparous: not</p>	<p>Hypnosis patients were self-selected and had generally expressed interest in hypnosis</p> <p>Women expressed interest in hypnosis to avoid epidural analgesia/ other interventions</p> <p>Women intending a natural childbirth might be expected to have a low rates interventions and epidurals</p>	<p>Pilot study for Cyna, Andrew, Robinson, Crowther, Baghurst, Turnbull, Wicks, & Whittle 2006</p>

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gestation				significantly different Augmentation rate Nulliparous 18% hypnosis 36% control Multiparous: not significantly different		
Compare hypnobirthing with standard childbirth classes on satisfaction with childbirth experience, anxiety with labor (Fisher, Esplin, Stoddard, & Silver, 2009)	RCT	38 women randomized -17 hypnobirth -21 standard classes Groups similar	Unknown at this time	Hypnobirthing perceived greater ability to cope during childbirth after course completion - Hypnobirth recalled relatively poorer intrapartum coping skill ($p = .02$) at delivery - No difference among groups in route of delivery, birth weight, Apgar scores, or intrapartum/postpartum epidural and analgesic use	Hypnobirthing was not more effective in improving perceived coping skills during labor than conational childbirth classes. -Small study -Unable to analyze	Study discussed at thirtieth annual meeting society for maternal-fetal medicine 2010. Only abstract available
Review of alternative medicine for labor pain (Huntley, Coon, & Ernst, 2004)	Systematic Review with 2 studies on hypnosis	Reviews by <i>American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology</i>	Reviewed: Freeman 1986 Harmon 1990	ACOG review states that studies analyzed suggest that hypnotic techniques may be useful for women during labor who are good hypnotic subjects	Further investigation is warranted	Used 2 of studies analyzed in systematic review done by Cyna, 2004
Cochrane Review of Hypnosis in labor as a	RCTs and quasi-randomized trials that	7 studies 1213 women total		- No significant differences between hypnosis and control group for use of pharmacological pain relief,	“There are still only a small number of studies assessing the use of hypnosis for labor and childbirth. Although the	

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form of pain management (Madden, Middleton, Cyna, Matthewson, & Jones, 2012)	compared preparation for labor using hypnosis			<p>spontaneous vaginal birth, satisfaction with pain relief, sense of coping with labor, satisfaction with childbirth, admissions to NICU, and breastfeeding at discharge.</p> <p>- Heterogeneous data for pharmacological pain relief and NSVD</p> <p>- Some evidence of benefit for length of labor, maternal hospital stay, and pain intensity.</p>	intervention shows some promise, further research is needed before recommendations can be made regarding its clinical usefulness for pain management in maternity care”	

Note. RCT = Randomized Control Trial; NRC = Non-randomized Control Trial; Pts = patients; Pt = patient; L&D = labor and delivery; ACOG = American Congress of Obstetricians and Gynecologists; CD = compact disc; NSVD = normal spontaneous vaginal delivery; NICU = neonatal intensive care unit.